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ENGINEERING OUR WAY TO A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE TOGETHER

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Topics: Lifelong Learning, Sustainability reflecting the complexity of modern society

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Learning outcomes (motivation & learning outcomes)

One of the outcomes of the workshop will be the creation of an ongoing community of practice in relation to engineering education and research and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDG).

A further outcome is that participants will improve insights into the UNSDG and their application to engineering education, research and active practice.

A third expected outcome will be acquaintance with sustainability initiatives and the use in their respective organisation and community.

A fourth outcome may be the involvement by each participant to contribute to the UNSDG repository of training materials in the SERINA initiative. Thereby having a relevant role in the creation of a better world.

Relevance

The motivation for this workshop was the IACEE Porto Declaration of 2016 and the related SERINA initiative concerning world sustainability (<http://serina.iacee.org/>). A partial transcription of the declaration says:

“...Now therefore in keeping with its dedication to leading lifelong learning, the IACEE will develop global initiatives to address those 21st century challenges threatening the survival of human kind through collaboration, design, creative thinking and engineering....”.

It is sought that engineering can help significantly to address the challenge of a sustainable world. SERINA is a promising and reliable approach to promote sustainability UN Goals among the engineering community. It is crucial to utilise in full

capacity the active engineers' competencies and influence enabling better sustainable decisions.

Participants role

Participants will be asked to establish and consider one sustainability initiative example taking place within their organisation or community relating to the UN SDGs. This example may also be chosen from the examples shared by the organisers. The active practice of engineers related with each example (projects, organisation or community) will be shared and discussed in small groups. The role of engineering education will be discussed and analysed in terms of benefits and implementation in a large scale.

Participants of the workshop will be introduced to and invited to be part of IACEE's Global Sustainability Initiative, SERINA, Sustainability Education and Research in Action. The role of the education initiative of SERINA, which is about highlighting and encouraging the work being done in organisations and communities around the world in sustainability, will be analysed. The SERINA initiative can be viewed and liked on Facebook... @serina.iacee, at the website serina.iacee.org or join the LinkedIn SERINA IACEE group.

Results summary

The structure of the workshop is composed by a brief presentation of United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, IACEE Porto Declaration and the SERINA initiative. Related copies of documents and web-links will be provided. Groups will be formed to address the questions presented. There will be in each group a member of IACEE and active in SERINA. There will be discussion among groups and proposals will be presented using digital support. Opinions of participants and answers to concrete questions will be recorded and shared using group digital communication tools. It is expected that there will be a set of proposals about next steps from the Engineering community to handle the challenge of a more effective participation.

Significance for Engineering Education

Engineering Education (EE) and Continuing Engineering Education (CEE) are crucial to handle the scale and complexity of the gap between existing solutions and the needs facing our planet. Engineers are uniquely placed to act on this opportunity. Through initiatives like SERINA it is possible to connect individuals, universities, industry, government and NGO organisations to meet the grand challenges facing humanity and the world.

Lifelong learning has developed and can continue to develop global initiatives to address those twenty-one century challenges threatening the survival of human kind through collaboration, design, creative thinking and engineering. The Porto Declaration (www.iacee.org) may motivate the engineering community and influence

a majority of stakeholders to comply with a framework of global sustainable development.

EE and CEE can influence on short term the pledge of the engineering community and of related sectors to a global commitment in implementing this call to service. This change and improvement can be obtained mostly by education and training of the engineering community around the world. Engineers and related stakeholders have a major influence in the world development. It is crucial that within a global and international arena the engineers take charge of the sustainable measures to ensure a future for the world. SERINA and the Porto Declaration can act as beacon and motivation for all and especially for active engineers and for future engineers. The contribution of these initiatives can arise from examples of related activities, the role of online learning in CEE sustainable courses, some guidelines for online sustainable courses and the provision of training and education for a sustainable world.